

Inventory of the ants of Nantucket
Final Report to NBI – 2007
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For summer of 2007, we (Aaron Ellison, Nick Gotelli, Stefan Cover, and Taber Allison) received \$1000 from NBI to support our work inventorying the ants of Nantucket. In addition to the field work conducted in July, we also worked with Scott Smyers to identify ants collected in pitfall traps set out in 2004, 2005, and 2006 by Aaron Weed and Mark Mello.

Initial results and analysis of this survey, with comparisons of the ant fauna among Nantucket, Martha's Vineyard, and Cape Cod, were presented by Ellison at the NBI meeting on Sept. 22, 2007. This meeting also provided Ellison with an opportunity to talk with Andrew McKenna-Foster, Cheryl Beaton, Aaron Weed, Mark Mello, and Karen Beattie about additional samples of ants available from Nantucket, Tuckernuck, and Muskeget Islands, ants in black-widow spider webs on Tuckernuck, and the impact of ants on nestling terns and plovers.

Our team sampled ants at two sites on Nantucket – at the Sesachaca Heathlands and the Coskata-Coatue Reservation. Within these sites, we sampled six habitats: a grassland, a heathland, and a scrub-oak shrubland at Sesachaca; and a maritime beach/dune; maritime juniper forest, and salt marsh berm at Coskata-Coatue. In the first four sites, we sampled full 75 × 75 m plots. The plot in the juniper forest was only 2,800 m², and the belt transect sampled at the salt marsh berm site at Coskata-Coatue was only 1,850 m². The grassland and heathland sites at Sesachaca were within the Dunwiddie vegetation plots currently being resampled by Ernie Steinauer and his colleagues.

Using hand collections and litter samples as described in our proposal, we collected 16 species in 9 genera representing 3 of the 4 subfamilies of ants known from Massachusetts (Table 1).

Table 1 – Occurrences of ant species at the sampled sites.

		Sesachaca			Coskata	Salt Marsh	
		Grass-land	Heath-land	Scrub Oak Shrubland	Maritime Beach/Dune	Maritime Juniper Forest	Berm
Dolichoderinae							
<i>Dolichoderus</i>	<i>plagiatus</i>			√			√
<i>Tapinoma</i>	<i>sessile</i>	√	√				
Myrmicinae							
<i>Aphaenogaster</i>	<i>fulva</i>	√					
<i>Aphaenogaster</i>	<i>rudis</i>	√		√			
<i>Aphaenogaster</i>	<i>treatae</i>	√	√				
<i>Crematogaster</i>	<i>lineolata</i>	√	√	√		√	
<i>Myrmica</i>	<i>americana</i>					√	
<i>Myrmica</i>	<i>fracticornis</i>		√				
<i>Tetramorium</i>	<i>caespitum</i>						√
Formicinae							
<i>Formica</i>	<i>incerta</i>					√	
<i>Formica</i>	<i>neogagates</i>					√	
<i>Formica</i>	<i>subsericea</i>				√	√	√
<i>Lasius</i>	<i>alienus</i>		√	√		√	
<i>Lasius</i>	<i>flavus</i>	√	√				
<i>Lasius</i>	<i>neoniger</i>				√	√	√
<i>Paratrechina</i>	<i>parvula</i>	√	√			√	

None of the ants are rare (and currently no ant species are listed by Massachusetts NHESP), although *Aphaenogaster fulva* is uncommonly collected. *Tetramorium caespitum* (the “pavement ant”) is not native to North America (it has a world-wide distribution), and is most common in sandy habitats such as beaches and dunes. *Lasius neoniger*, the most common ant that we collected, is also apparently common in tern nests infested with ants (based on samples from Monomoy and Osterville provided by Robert Buchsbaum to Aaron Ellison).

Ants were also sorted from pitfall traps collected at Ram Pasture in 2006 by Aaron Weed and Mark Mello, and provided to Ellison by Scott Smyers (ants from 2004 and 2005 pitfalls have not yet been sorted out by Weed, Mello, or Smyers). In these collections, we identified 27 species in 16 genera from all 4 subfamilies known to occur in Massachusetts:

Dolichoderinae

Dolichoderus pustulatus

Tapinoma sessile

Myrmicinae

Aphaenogaster rudis

Aphaenogaster treatae

Monomorium emarginatum

Myrmecina americana

Myrmica americana

Myrmica pinetorum

Myrmica punctiventris

Myrmica “sculptilis” (unpublished species, fide Andre Franceour)

Myrmica “smithana” (unpublished species, fide Andre Franceour)

Solenopsis molesta

Stenamma impar

Formicinae

Brachymyrmex depilis

Camponotus noveboracensis

Crematogaster lineolata

Formica incerta

Formica neogagates

Formica subsericea

Lasius alienus

Lasius flavus

Lasius nearcticus

Lasius (Acanthomyops) latipes

Lasius (Acanthomyops) subglaber

Paratrechina parvula

Ponerinae

Amblyopone pallipes

Ponera pennsylvanica

Five species (*Dolichoderus plagiatus*, *Aphaenogaster fulva*, *Myrmica fracticornis*, *Tetramorium caespitum*, *Lasius neoniger*) collected by our group were not found in the Weed/Mello pitfalls. Several other species were listed by Wheeler (1928) as occurring on Nantucket: *Formica dolosa*, *F. pallidefulva*, *F. difficilis*, *F. exsectoides*, *F. obscuriventris*, *Monomorium minimum* (modern nomenclature follows

Bolton et al. 2006 and Trager et al. *in press*). Combining our collections, the Weed/Mello pitfalls, and Wheeler's historical records suggests that at least 38 ant species could be extant on Nantucket. This is just under 40% of the species recorded in all of Massachusetts (based on Stefan Cover's unpublished list).

Digital images

We have not yet taken photos of the specimens, but photos of all species are available for free download and non-commercial use from the California Academy of Sciences AntWeb project (<http://antweb.org/>). We are also preparing a permanent educational display on the Ants of Nantucket for the Maria Mitchell Museum. We hope to complete that for delivery by May 2008.

Literature Cited

- Bolton, B., G. Alpert, P. S. Ward, and P. Naskrecki. 2006. *Bolton's Catalogue of Ants of the World: 1758-2005*. Harvard University Press, Cambridge, MA.
- Trager, J. C., J. A. MacGown, and M. D. Trager. *In press*. Revision of the Nearctic endemic *Formica pallidefulva* group. *To appear in: Annals of the Entomological Institute*.
- Wheeler, W. M. 1928. Ants of Nantucket Island, Mass. *Psyche* 35: 10-11.